

• Dissemination Exploitation and Communication Plan

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Abstract

The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan is a guideline for all communication activities and dissemination measures of the GraspOS project. It outlines how communication and dissemination can contribute to maximising exploitation of the project results. The plan will be used for the implementation of the day-by-day activities and therefore continuously monitored and updated to also cover activities which will continue after the end of the project.

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Abbreviation List

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
CoP	Community of Practice
CRIS	Current Research Information System
DECP	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A	European Open Science Cloud Association
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OA	Open Access
OSAF	Open Science Assessment Framework

OSAR	Open Science Assessment Registry
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
RRA	Responsible Research Assessment
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

● Executive Summary

The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (DECP) is a strategic living document containing the activities to be set up and implemented to maximise the project's outreach and impact.

The DECP aims to promote, raise awareness and enhance the visibility of the project in order to effectively reach the wide range of stakeholders targeted by the project activities. The implementation of our Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication strategy and its main tools and channels are defined within the document with a view to maximising outreach and engagement.

The plan is structured as follows:

1. The core messages of the project and its visual identity are presented, including GraspOS' main objectives and areas of impact.
2. The target audiences the project aims to reach are described.
3. The core of the document regards the strategy we have set up and deployed to reach the communication and dissemination objectives of the project.

4. How GraspOS will align its communication strategy with project partners and related infrastructures, projects and initiatives is explained.
5. The potential challenges related to communication that may arise within the project are listed with ways to address them.
6. The exploitation section documents all processes on how external stakeholders will interact with the project to realise a substantial uptake.

- **Methodology**

Not applicable.

● Introduction

GraspOS is a Horizon Europe research project focused on creating an **open research assessment dataspace**¹. It aims to provide data, tools, services and guidance to support and **enable policy reforms for Open Science-aware Responsible Research Assessment (RRA)** at various levels including researchers, institutions, organisations and countries.

The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (DECP) is a guideline for all communication activities and dissemination measures of the GraspOS project partners. It outlines how communication and dissemination can contribute to maximising exploitation of the project results. The DECP will be used for the implementation of the day-by-day activities and therefore continuously monitored and updated to also cover activities which will continue after the end of the project.

The main objectives of the DECP have been defined as follows:

- **build awareness about the project;**
- **lay down the foundations for effective communication of the project's concept and potential benefits to interested stakeholders;**
- **communicate research findings so as to stimulate ongoing interest in the work of the project;**
- **build the foundations for future partnerships among the engaged stakeholders;**
- **maximise the project's impact;**
- **maximise exploitation opportunities of the project throughout and beyond its development.**

In the first section, we identify the core messages of the GraspOS project, including its main objectives and areas of impact according to the stakeholder categories targeted by the project. The visual identity for GraspOS is presented along with an overview of the communication materials which have been created in the first phase of the project. In the second section, GraspOS target stakeholders are described in detail, including their needs and key messages for each group. In the third section, we present the overall communication and dissemination strategy and provide detail on the online channels we make use of to reach the GraspOS target audiences. In the fourth section, we describe how GraspOS will align its communication strategy with project partners and related infrastructures, projects and initiatives. The potential risks related to communication and how they can be addressed are presented in section 5. The last section is dedicated to the Exploitation plan.

¹ We follow the Data Spaces Support Centre's definition of data space as defined in the DSSC Glossary: "An infrastructure that enables data transactions between different data ecosystem parties based on the governance framework of that data space. Data space should be generic enough to support the implementation of multiple use cases".
<https://dssc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/DSSC-Data-Spaces-Glossary-v1.0.pdf>

1. GraspOS core messages to communicate

The core messages and figures of the GraspOS project are outlined in the following section.

○ 1.1 Key facts about the GraspOS project

- GraspOS stands for **next Generation Research Assessment to Promote Open Science**.
- Launch: 1 January 2023
- Project duration: 36 months
- Funded under the Horizon Europe framework programme with approx. € 2.9 million Euros.
- [Consortium](#) of 18 partners located in 10 European countries
- Coordinated from Greece by [Athena Research Center](#)
- Approx. 110 staff members contributing work to one or more of the seven Work Packages (WPs).
- [Nine pilots](#) to co-design, showcase, validate and evaluate OS-aware RRA indicators, tools and services.

○ 1.2 GraspOS objectives and impacts

GraspOS' main objectives and areas of impact represent the project's unique selling point. The overall objective of the project is to enable a rewards and recognition system based on a new generation of qualitative and quantitative metrics and indicators, leading to a culture and system change that increases the quality and impact, the creativity and the transparency of and trust in science, and to establish a system of qualitative information based on community-led curation and annotations of research outcomes that feeds into a revamped rewards and recognition system.

In order to achieve this goal, the project aims to develop, assess and put into operation an open dataspace for next generation research metrics and indicators, offering data, tools, services and guidance to support and enable policy reforms for research assessment at researcher, institutional, organisational and country level.

GraspOS' key objectives to achieve this are represented in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1 Main objectives of the GraspOS project

GraspOS aims to:

- Deliver an **Open Science Assessment Framework (OSAF)** as a toolkit to assist research funding and performing organisations in tailoring and implementing new generation, Open Science-aware RRA approaches.
- Develop and deliver a set of **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)-integrated, Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven metadata enrichment tools and services** for enhancing missing attributes and novel indicator values on research outputs to support the implementation of new generation, Open Science-aware RRA approaches.
- Build an **EOSC-integrated, open research assessment dataspace** providing data, tools, and services to support the implementation of new generation, Open Science-aware RRA approaches.
- Empower and bring together different stakeholder communities to **co-design, showcase, validate, and evaluate** Open Science-aware RRA indicators, tools, services and infrastructure in **real-world pilots**.

The main impacts of GraspOS are represented in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2 Main impacts the GraspOS project aims for

The main impacts the GraspOS project aims for are detailed below with the principal stakeholder groups who are expected to benefit from these. Further information on each stakeholder group is available in Section 2.

Improve transparency, creativity and trust in research assessment. GraspOS will facilitate the move from evaluation approaches based on bibliometrics indicators towards more responsible approaches to research assessment. The project will support the European Commission (EC) in challenging the *status quo* by building an open research assessment dataspace available in the EOSC shaped by the research community for the research community.

Target groups:

- *Researchers*
- *Research funding organisations (RFOs) and research performing organisations (RPOs)*
- *Experts and initiatives*

Transform the way research funders, organisations and communities perform research assessment. GraspOS will guide research funders, organisations and communities in using the assessment processes and protocols and will provide them with data, off-the-shelf metrics and supporting tools and training. In addition to the Open research assessment dataspace, project results such as the OSAF, the OSAR, the Openness Profile templates and the Dashboards will provide practical experience to research groups, research organisations and

funders to shape and select their own assessment pathways beyond the traditional research assessment metrics.

Target groups:

- *Researchers*
- *RFOs and RPOs*

Generate new data and develop new tools enabling qualitative research assessment.

GraspOS aims to provide the infrastructure for collecting and enriching large-scale meta-research data and to develop and deploy intelligent and novel tools and services to support the generation of new and qualitative data and metrics for Open Science production, practice, usage and impact.

Target groups:

- *Researchers*
- *RFOs and RPOs*
- *Research infrastructures*
- *Developers*
- *EOSC ecosystem*

Contribute to EOSC Core and provide EOSC native services for research assessment on Open Science.

GraspOS will contribute to the EOSC Interoperability Framework by extending existing guidelines and best practices on how to present and exchange metrics data, information relevant to Open Science graphs and usage metrics. GraspOS will enrich the EOSC offer (via EOSC Exchange) with the tools and services developed in WP3 and will make the EOSC an integral part of the research assessment by investigating potential relevant metrics derived by the usage or adoption of EOSC services.

Target groups:

- *Research infrastructures*
- *EOSC ecosystem*

○ 1.3 GraspOS visual identity

The development of the project's visual identity has been a core element of the overall communication and dissemination strategy. As a project Milestone, GraspOS visual identity was delivered in M4, taking into account the Co-branding guidelines for Horizon Europe INFRAEOSC Project proposed by the EOSC Association (EOSC-A)².

² Co-branding guidelines for Horizon Europe INFRAEOSC Project proposed by the EOSC Association, August 2022.

[https://eosc.eu/sites/default/files/20220822_Co-Branding%20Guidelines%20for%20HE%20INFRAEOSC%20Projects 4 EOSC-A final.pdf](https://eosc.eu/sites/default/files/20220822_Co-Branding%20Guidelines%20for%20HE%20INFRAEOSC%20Projects%204%20EOSC-A%20final.pdf)

The official project logo (Figure 3) must be used in all project documents and is always accompanied by the tagline “open research assessment dataspace”. In specific occurrences (website footer, social media banners and external presentations) the GraspOS logo is showcased along with the ‘supporting EOSC’ logo in a smaller size (Figure 4)³.

Figure 3 Project logo and tagline

Figure 4 Supporting EOSC logo

A toolkit containing all the necessary material and information to produce the project outcomes following GraspOS visual identity (logo, deliverables and presentations templates) was created and made available in the Deliverable D1.1 “Project Management Guide” (DOI [10.5281/zenodo.8069009](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8069009)).

Documenting the visual identity elements and providing guidelines on how to use them is critical to maintain consistency. GraspOS brand guidelines have been created to support project partners in the use of the visual identity materials. The document outlines specifications for logo usage, colour codes, typography rules, and provides examples of how the visual identity should be applied across different mediums. The GraspOS brand guidelines are provided in this file and have been added in Annex 1.

○ 1.4 GraspOS communication materials

In the initial phase of the project, the following materials have been created:

- **Banners for the GraspOS website** (Figure 5) and social media channels Twitter, LinkedIn, and Mastodon (see Section 3.3 for further details on the social media channels) which can also be used for other relevant communication and promotional materials. For the website, an additional set of images were created in line with

³ Corporate Design Manual of the EOSC Association, September 2022.

https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/2022-09/EOSC%20Corporate%20Design%20Manual_HR.pdf

GraspOS visual identity, they are also relevant for other communication purposes and can be applied to various mediums.

Figure 5 GraspOS website banner

- A **poster** with concise information about the project has been created. It is uploaded to the project's Google Drive folder, to the project website (<https://graspOS.eu/dissemination-toolkit>), and is deposited on Zenodo (DOI [10.5281/zenodo.8075017](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8075017)).
- **Tailored visuals** have been created to communicate GraspOS messages or promote specific project activities on the website and on social media. Figure 6 is provided below as an example of tailored visuals to promote GraspOS activities. This visual was created to promote a landscaping survey prepared by WP2 as a news item on the project website and was adapted for social media. The same strategy will be adopted for all visuals that promote or communicate GraspOS activities.

Figure 6 Visual for GraspOS website news item

In the next phase of the project, we plan to create specific visuals for the following:

- Interviews to present GraspOS partners
- Interviews of GraspOS pilots
- GraspOS monthly newsletter

○ 1.5 Language-related aspects of communication

When sharing information about the GraspOS project through the website or social media channels and when producing communication materials, we pay attention to some general language-related aspects that have been identified below. These are also considered useful for reviewers and proofreaders of communication materials.

Following the United Nations guidelines for gender inclusive English⁴, we try to make gender not visible when it is not relevant. Communication is tailored to the respective audiences (in terms of language, wording, style and complexity). When communicating to non-specialist target audiences, accessibility is ensured by keeping messages concise and simple.

⁴ United Nations, Guidelines for gender-inclusive language in English. <https://www.un.org/en/gender-inclusive-language/guidelines.shtml>

As much as possible, and when relevant, communications are translated in the native language of the target audience. We expect this to be relevant in the case of national or local workshop announcements which will take place in another language than English. We plan to rely on the respective partners to translate content in their native language.

To highlight the impact of our activities and raise awareness among our target audiences, we will use storytelling techniques. The success stories presented in section 3.9 are expected to be written following the example of the Research and Innovation Projects Success stories page of the European Commission (<https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/projects/success-stories>).

2. GraspOS target audiences and value proposition

o 2.1 Target audiences

An effective **understanding of all stakeholder groups** that need to be mobilised from the beginning to ensure the success of the project is critical to help co-create and inform all project outcomes. Additionally, exploring and understanding the **motivations and needs** of each group will help create open communication lines with each of the stakeholders and ensure their involvement and engagement throughout the project thus contributing to the success and longevity of the project results.

GraspOS targets a broad range of stakeholders, the key target audiences which have been identified and prioritised are outlined in Table 1 below and further detailed in the following subsections. The target audiences will be approached during year 1 and year 2 of the project, they are expected to inform the project's final results on year 3.

Table 1 GraspOS Stakeholder categories

6 stakeholder categories		
1	Researchers	Individuals and groups of researchers
2	RPOs and RFOs	Research performing organisations and research funders
3	Initiatives and frameworks	Research assessment experts and relevant initiatives working on reforming research assessment

4	Research infrastructures	Relevant data providers, National Current Research Information System (CRIS) developers and Developers of research assessment systems at research organisations
5	Assessment experts	RRA experts and researchers, Scientometric experts and AI/data experts
6	EOSC	EOSC ecosystem

■ 2.1.1 Researchers

This category includes researchers, described in the [European Charter and Code](#) as “Professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems, and in the management of the projects concerned.” More specifically, it comprises all persons professionally engaged in Research & Development at any career stage, regardless of their classification. This includes any activities related to “basic research”, “strategic research”, “applied research”, experimental development and “transfer of knowledge” including innovation and advisory, supervisory and teaching capacities, the management of knowledge and intellectual property rights, the exploitation of research results or scientific journalism.

In this category we include not only individual researchers, but also representative organisations such as:

- Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, an umbrella association or National associations representing early-career researchers in the European Area (eurodoc.net).
- Academia Europea, the Pan-European Academy of Sciences Humanities and Letters (<https://www.ae-info.org/>).
- MCAA, the Marie Curie Alumni Association, representing all individual researchers that have benefited from the [Marie Curie Skłodowska Actions grant](#) in the European Framework Programs of the EC (mariecuriealumni.eu).
- [Global Young Academy](#) and [Young Academy of Europe](#), associations representing junior principal investigators and junior researchers.
- ISE, Initiative for Science in Europe, an independent platform of European Learned Societies and Research Organisations. It involves researchers in the design and implementation of European science policies, and advocates for strong independent scientific advice in European policy making (initiative-se.eu).
- ALLEA, the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities (<https://allea.org/>).

All of those associations have been involved in the research assessment discussion from the EC Scoping Report⁵ to the signature of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment⁶.

Other researchers may be involved through the following channels:

- [EOSC Association Task Forces](#), in particular those involved in the Research Careers and Curricula.
- RDA, Research Data Alliance, a community-driven initiative which involves research data experts (not only researchers) ([rd-alliance.org](#)).
- IGDORE, Institute for Globally Distributed Open Research and Education, an independent research institute dedicated to improving the quality of science, science education, and quality of life for scientists, students and their families. It is composed by individual researchers advocating and practising Open Science ([igdore.org](#)).

■ 2.1.2 RPOs and RFOs

This category includes Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs). RPOs are Higher Education Institutions, including Universities and Universities of Applied Sciences, Public Research Institutes, Research Centres that are providing infrastructures and services enabling professionals to perform research activities. RFOs include public and private funders for research and innovation and evaluation agencies.

In this category we include representative organisations and signatory RPOs and RFOs of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment such as:

- EUA, European University Association ([eua.eu](#))
- Science Europe ([scienceeurope.org](#))
- cOAlition S ([coalition-s.org](#))
- LERU ([leru.org](#))
- YERUN ([yerun.eu](#))
- Coimbra Group ([coimbra-group.eu](#))
- UNICA ([unica-network.eu](#))
- CESAER ([cesaer.org](#))
- ALLEA ([allea.org](#))
- EARTO ([earto.eu](#))
- EARMA ([earma.org](#))

⁵ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Towards a reform of the research assessment system – Scoping report, Publications Office, 2021.
<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/707440>

⁶ Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment, July 2022.
https://coara.eu/app/uploads/2022/09/2022_07_19_rra_agreement_final.pdf

- The Guild (the-guild.eu)
- ECIU (<https://www.eciu.eu/>)
- EURASHE (<https://www.eurashe.eu/>)
- EUHA (<https://www.euhalliance.eu/>)
- UAS4EUROPE (<https://uas4europe.eu/>)
- UKRI (<https://www.ukri.org/>)
- Erasmus + and Universities Research Alliances
- Any RPOs and RFOs who have signed [CoARA](#) and [DORA](#)

■ 2.1.3 Initiatives and frameworks

Relevant initiatives in the field of research assessment refer to programs, projects, or activities aimed at improving and refining the assessment processes and methodologies in research. These initiatives are often driven by the need to ensure fairness, transparency, and accountability in research evaluation, as well as to foster research excellence and innovation. They may involve the development of new evaluation metrics, the establishment of standardised assessment frameworks, the promotion of responsible research practices, or the implementation of open science principles.

Examples of relevant initiatives in the research assessment domain include:

1. Initiatives for responsible research assessment

- San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) (<https://sfdora.org/>)
- Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics (<http://www.leidenmanifesto.org/>)
- The Hong Kong Principles for assessing researchers (<https://journals.plos.org/plosbiology/article?id=10.1371/journal.pbio.3000737>)
- Recognition & Rewards programme (<https://recognitionrewards.nl/>)
- Alternative Assessment Metrics (Altmetrics) Initiative (<https://www.niso.org/standards-committees/altmetrics>)
- OpenCitations (<https://opencitations.net/>)

2. Research Assessment Frameworks

- Research Excellence Framework (REF) (<https://www.ref.ac.uk/>)
- Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP) (https://storage.knaw.nl/2022-06/SEP_2021-2027.pdf)
- INORMS SCOPE Framework for Research Evaluation (<https://inorms.net/scope-framework-for-research-evaluation/>)

3. Open Science initiatives

These initiatives promote the adoption of open and transparent practices in research, including the sharing of data, methodologies, and research findings. They seek to enhance

research reproducibility, collaboration, and the assessment of research impact beyond traditional metrics. For example, we include here:

- SPARC (<https://sparcopen.org/>)
- TOPS (<https://science.nasa.gov/open-science/transform-to-open-science>)
- UNESCO Working Groups (WGs) on Open Science (<https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science>)
- RDA WG (<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/working-groups>) related to research assessment

4. EU Projects

We aim to bridge synergies with other EC-funded projects such as:

- OPUS (<https://opusproject.eu>)
- PathOS (<https://pathos-project.eu/>)
- SciLake (<https://scilake.eu/>)

■ 2.1.4 Research infrastructures

In this category, key players involved in the provision of relevant research data, in the development of national CRIS platforms, and in the creation of research assessment systems within research organisations are represented. They contribute to the infrastructure, tools, and resources necessary for effective research assessment and evaluation. This category includes:

1. Data providers

Relevant data providers include academic repositories, databases, publishers, funding agencies, government bodies, and research institutions themselves. They gather and maintain various types of data, such as research outputs (e.g., publications, patents), funding information, collaboration networks, citation data, and research impact indicators. Relevant data providers play a crucial role in supplying the necessary data for research assessment exercises and supporting evidence-based evaluations.

Examples of these categories are research e-infrastructures such as those in the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) (<https://www.esfri.eu/>) or they can be registries, publishers, funding agencies, and other Persistent Identifier (PID) authorities.

2. European and National CRIS

CRIS stands for Current Research Information System. National CRIS are entities or organisations responsible for developing and maintaining CRIS platforms at a national level. A CRIS is a comprehensive repository or software system that integrates and manages research-related information, including research outputs, funding information, researcher

profiles, and collaboration networks. National CRIS work closely with research institutions, funding agencies, and other stakeholders to design, implement, and enhance CRIS platforms. These systems facilitate the collection, organisation, and sharing of research information, supporting research assessment and decision-making processes. At European level, EuroCRIS brings together experts on research information and CRIS to foster cooperation and knowledge-sharing across the research information community and to promote interoperability of research information (<https://eurocris.org/>)

OpenAIRE members and similar e-infrastructures communities such as the Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR) gather those developers. We will also engage with librarians and other CRIS managers worldwide.

3. Developers of research assessment systems at research organisations

Developers of research assessment systems at research organisations are professionals or teams responsible for creating and managing assessment systems within specific research institutions or organisations. These systems are designed to evaluate the research performance, impact, and quality of individual researchers, research groups, or the institution as a whole.

■ 2.1.5 Assessment experts

Research assessment experts are professionals who specialise in evaluating and analysing research outputs, performance, and impact. Researchers performing Research on Research may also be included in this category. They play a crucial role in assessing the quality, significance, and contribution of research activities conducted by individuals, institutions, or groups. These experts employ various methodologies, metrics, and evaluation frameworks to provide an objective and comprehensive assessment of research work. These categories represent individuals who specialise in different aspects of research assessment, including the evaluation of research outputs, the quantitative analysis of research publications and data, and the application of AI and data analysis techniques to enhance research assessment practices. More specifically:

1. RRA experts and researchers

RRA experts are involved in conducting research studies, analysing research outputs, and providing insights into research assessment processes. They may contribute to the development of evaluation methodologies, the design of research assessment systems, or the formulation of policies related to research quality and impact.

2. Scientometric experts

Scientometric experts are professionals who specialise in scientometrics, a field that focuses on the quantitative analysis of scientific publications and related data. They employ statistical and computational methods to study scientific publications, citation patterns, collaborations, and other aspects of scientific research. Scientometric experts use bibliometric data to examine the impact, visibility, and influence of individual researchers, institutions, or research

areas. They contribute to the understanding of scientific trends, knowledge diffusion, and the assessment of research productivity and impact.

3. AI and data experts

AI/data experts are professionals that possess knowledge of machine learning algorithms, data mining techniques, and statistical modelling. In the context of research assessment, AI/data experts develop AI-based tools and algorithms to automate the analysis of research outputs, identify patterns and trends, and extract insights from research data.

■ 2.1.6 EOSC ecosystem

The EOSC ecosystem is a dynamic and evolving community that brings together stakeholders from different sectors and disciplines to foster open science principles, enable data sharing, and facilitate collaborative research. It promotes the seamless exchange of data, tools, and knowledge, while supporting the needs of researchers, institutions, and other actors within the European research landscape. EOSC is an initiative funded by the EC that aims to create a shared infrastructure for open and accessible research data and services across Europe. The “EOSC ecosystem” includes the EOSC Association and the stakeholders contributing to EOSC-related projects.

The EOSC ecosystem encompasses various components and actors, including:

1. EOSC Association (EOSC-A)

The EOSC-A (<https://eosc.eu/eosc-association>) is an international non-profit organisation that oversees the implementation and governance of the EOSC. It brings together stakeholders from research communities, e-infrastructures, and service providers to drive the development and sustainability of the EOSC. The association plays a key role in coordinating and aligning efforts within the EOSC ecosystem and represents the interests of its members in shaping the future of open science in Europe.

2. EOSC-A Task Forces

Within the EOSC-A, there are various task forces dedicated to specific areas of focus (<https://eosc.eu/eosc-task-forces>). One relevant task force is the Research Careers and Curricula task force. This task force focuses on addressing the needs and requirements related to research careers, skills development, and training within the EOSC ecosystem. It aims to foster the development of research careers, promote Open Science skills, and ensure a diverse and inclusive research environment.

3. EOSC Projects

EOSC projects are initiatives and collaborative efforts that contribute to the development, implementation, and enhancement of the EOSC. These projects receive funding and support from the EC and focus on various aspects, such as infrastructure development, data management, interoperability, and service provision within the EOSC. They play a crucial role

in advancing the capabilities and functionalities of the EOSC, ensuring its sustainability, and promoting Open Science practices across Europe.

○ 2.2 GraspOS Value proposition

This section outlines the main needs we have identified for GraspOS target audiences and presents the project's key results along with targeted messages for each stakeholder group.

■ 2.2.1 Audience needs

Below is a non-exhaustive list of the main needs of GraspOS target audience with regard to the project's aims.

- Change the way research assessment is performed
- Community-designed toolkit for RRA and alignment with current initiatives
- No-paywall data infrastructure in support of RRA
- Trust in tools, services, and infrastructures for RRA, interoperable with EOSC
- Qualitative research assessment by generating new data, developing new tools and interoperating with existing services
- Enriching the EOSC offer and interoperate a RRA tool with EOSC and its resources

We will ensure that the project results described in the following section will effectively address the aforementioned needs.

■ 2.2.2 Key results

The key exploitable project outputs reported in Table 2 below will be addressed by the communication and dissemination and exploitation measures in later stages of the project.

Table 2 GraspOS Key exploitable results

Key result	Explanation
Open Science Assessment Framework	Living and collaborative guide detailing indicator toolboxes and metrics capturing different Open Science practices and activities in various contexts.
Openness Profiles	RRA templates which can be used as fit-for-purpose templates for collecting and structuring both quantitative and qualitative indicators.
Open Science Assessment Registry	An online database of OSAF-based Openness profiles and case studies in a structured and systematic way to promote experience sharing and mutual learning.
AI-driven Metadata Enrichment Tools and Services	A set of tools and services to enhance missing attributes on research outputs, enrich research outputs links with semantics, and with novel metrics capturing scientific impact or usage of Open Science from different perspectives (short or long term; scientific collaboration impact)

Open Science Monitoring Tools and Services	The Open Science Institutional Dashboard is a tailor-made Open Science profile for RPOs and the Open Science Researcher Dashboard is a tailor-made Open Science profile for researchers which offers Open Science metrics, manual annotations and narrative functions.
EOSC-integrated Open and Federated Research Assessment Dataspace	A federated infrastructure that extends the EOSC interoperability framework (EIF) with the appropriate metadata standards, protocols, components and APIs to support AI-driven annotation and enrichment and to implement an EOSC Core Metrics service based on the integration of key GraspOS components.
Open Science-aware RRA pilots	Nine pilot studies to co-design, showcase, validate and evaluate GraspOS' key results considering domain-specific aspects at different levels of OS-aware RRA.
Community of Practice of Open Science-aware experts	A diverse community of RRA experts from relevant networks.
Training materials	A set of carefully designed training material accessible via the EOSC knowledge hub.

■ 2.2.3 Tailored messages

Formulating a clear value proposition for each of the stakeholder groups addressed by the project is critical to communicate the project offering in a clear and compelling manner. At the beginning of the project, GraspOS stakeholders and key messages have been defined as presented in Table 3 below. In successive stages of the project, a more detailed value proposition will be set up for each of GraspOS' key stakeholder groups to help us propose a targeted offering.

Table 3 GraspOS stakeholders and key messages

Stakeholders	Key Messages
Researchers	The new OSAF framework allows to take into account new quantitative and qualitative aspects related to Open Science practices performed by individuals that can complement the pure traditional quantitative evaluation based on publications. The tools and services developed by GraspOS can also facilitate the collection of this information.
RPOs and RFOs	GraspOS can provide to RPOs and RFOs structured standard frameworks that can easily be adopted and adapted according to the different needs (existing barriers in place, disciplinary needs, geographical needs). The Open and Federated Research Assessment Dataspace developed by GraspOS will improve the trust in infrastructures for RPOs and RFOs in relation to research assessment by improving the quality and availability of data needed for assessment practices. GraspOS will also facilitate the interaction and experience exchange among a broad range of RPOs and RFOs.

Initiatives and frameworks	GraspOS will provide research assessment experts and related initiatives a platform to discuss and co-develop the research assessment frameworks of the future. The project will offer networking opportunities and the possibility of sharing results and lessons learnt from the different initiatives. GraspOS will take into account the fundamental role communities of practice play in shaping the current research assessment system and in transitioning towards more responsible and more open assessment practices. The project will co-develop and build synergies with these communities.
Research infrastructures	GraspOS will provide an infrastructure to enable a reformed research assessment system that aims to be interoperable with existing systems (e.g., CRIS, university research assessment systems, etc.) and that allows scalability. Data providers like the OpenAIRE Research Graph will be able to feed and retrieve information from the new established infrastructure to enrich the available data.
Assessment experts	GraspOS will engage with experts and researchers in RRA (e.g., via the Super Morri national nodes), the Scientometrics community and AI researchers and experts who are developing novel services. The project will attract them into using the data, evaluating the services, proposing new indicators, and using the underlying infrastructure as a sandbox for novel AI tools and new, innovative metrics.
EOSC ecosystem	GraspOS will work in close collaboration with the EOSC projects awarded in this call and the EOSC projects in charge of the development of the EOSC Core and Exchange to ensure a smooth integration of the services developed by GraspOS. In addition, the project will work towards the inclusion of EOSC practices in the research assessment evaluation and monitoring (for example, the usage of EOSC services, etc.).

3. Communication and dissemination channels and measures

○ 3.1 Overall strategy and implementation

This section presents the GraspOS communication and dissemination strategy by detailing how the measures to maximise outreach which have been defined at the beginning of the project are implemented and through which channel. Tools created internally to support the organisation of the work in WP6 are also presented here.

The communication and dissemination activities will be performed by the project to promote its results beyond the project's community throughout the full duration of the project and beyond. The project will also communicate and disseminate the project's research and its benefits for society in a non-specialist way.

In the initial phase of the project, the measures focus on communicating about GraspOS objectives and activities through the various channels detailed in the sections below. In the next phase of the project, we will focus on disseminating the results and outcomes of GraspOS following the project evolution.

Two tools were created to facilitate the management of communication and dissemination activities across the project and with WP6 project partners.

- (1) A shared spreadsheet serves as a planning and reporting tool regarding the dissemination of project results (for now it includes events in which GraspOS is presented and publications). The purpose of the file is to ensure that all project outputs are consistently disseminated to maximise outreach and impact and to facilitate collaboration in doing so. It is available in Annex 2.
- (2) In order to align content across GraspOS communication channels, a Content planning tool has been created internally and is used within T6.1 to manage content on the project website and on social media consistently. In order to facilitate the sharing of information from WP6 towards external stakeholders, a list with project partners' online information is included in this tool (Annex 3) along with a list of high impact accounts and most relevant hashtags on Twitter (Annex 4).

The main communication and dissemination channels are outlined in the bullet points below. For each point, specific communication and dissemination measures will be set up and implemented, they are detailed in the following subsections.

- **Website:** The GraspOS project website (delivered in M3) is the main channel to communicate and disseminate the outcomes of the project.
- **Social media:** A social media strategy has been set up and implemented to complement the project's digital impact.
- **Newsletter:** A monthly newsletter (start M6) will inform relevant stakeholders about the progress and results of the project.
- **Stakeholder consultations:**
 - Community of Practice (CoP): the CoP consists of actors involved in Open Science practices and in developing new recognition and reward systems. It will bring together diverse groups of actors involved in the design, development, testing and validation of the infrastructure.
 - Pilots: the 9 pilots will organise workshops with national and institutional stakeholders also including individuals, they also aim at organising interviews, surveys and focus groups with relevant stakeholders.
- **GraspOS webinars and events:** 2 webinars per year will be organised to establish a dialogue with the broader community.
- **Events:** The project partners will be attending events, including conferences and workshops addressing topics related to research careers and incentives, research assessment of Open Science and EOSC-related events to present the results of the project and to understand how the landscape is developing.

- **6 training tutorials** will be developed to educate the pilot participants and the external stakeholders on the benefits of adopting the new OSAF and on how to use the services and the infrastructure developed by WP3 and WP4.
- **Publications:** the aim is to publish GraspOS research outputs in Open Access (OA) journals and platforms and/or to store them in OA repositories.
- **Success stories** from the pilots to encourage new stakeholders with similar needs to reform their research assessment practices.
- **Final brief:** a final report containing guidelines and lessons learnt will be produced by the project at M34.

The communication and dissemination measures listed above reflect the variety of channels we will make use of to effectively reach out to the various stakeholder groups targeted by GraspOS.

The following Key performance indicators (KPIs) serve as a baseline to quantify positive evolutions or needs for improvement in the communication and dissemination strategy. They are listed in Table 4 along with the state of progress at M6.

Table 4 Communication and dissemination KPIs

Channel	Activity	KPI	Measure	M6
Project website	main source for outputs and news	# visitors	>200 unique monthly visitors	A usage tracking tool will be set up in the next phase of the project.
Social Media (Twitter, LinkedIn, Mastodon)	project specific social media profiles for dissemination and communication purposes, including video tutorials	# followers	> 500 Twitter followers	258 Twitter followers
Newsletter	Disseminating project-specific content and news to subscribers	# newsletters	monthly newsletter	Activity starts at M6
Training tutorials	Training and co-design workshops organised by the project	# events	6 training tutorials, engaging overall 300 participants	Activity starts at M12
GraspOS webinars	2 webinars per year organised by the project	# events	6 webinars targeting 240 participants	2 webinars are in preparation
GraspOS final conference	1 final F2F conference	# participants	Minimum 100 participants	N/A

Participation in external events	promoting project outputs at external events	# of events with contributions from project partners	> 30 events	5 events completed, 4 in preparation
Scientific publications	OA journals and platforms	# publications	4 research outputs	1 peer-reviewed publication

○ 3.2 Website

The GraspOS project website (<https://graspos.eu/>) was delivered in M3, it is the main channel to communicate and disseminate the outcomes of the project. To deliver the project's messages across the stakeholder groups identified in section 2.1, a digital ecosystem has been created with the aim to boost the online presence of the project and reach out to key stakeholders effectively. In the first months of the project, a jointly coordinated approach has been set up between WP6 partners to efficiently manage the flow of information between the project website and the various communication and dissemination channels.

The digital ecosystem is represented below in Figure 7 and highlights the central role of the project website in the communication and dissemination strategy. Information is shared from the website towards external channels which act as amplifiers (by re-sharing the information to other networks of stakeholders). Some of the external channels are managed by GraspOS and represent GraspOS communities on different social media platforms (Twitter, Mastodon, LinkedIn). In other cases, the project relies on a strong and reliable network of experienced stakeholders to circulate information and on external stakeholders such as the EOSC-A and the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA).

This strategy has the double advantage of considering the project website as the source of communication and dissemination activities while also bringing traffic to the website.

Figure 7 GraspOS digital ecosystem

The website is structured to provide targeted information to GraspOS key stakeholders, mainly researchers and research performing and funding organisations. The structure of the website is reported below, the main sections foresee the communication and dissemination activities that will be carried out throughout the duration of the project.

About

Methodology

Pilots

Dissemination Toolkit

Partners

Activities and Results

Deliverables

Open Science Assessment Framework

Open Science Assessment Registry

Open Science Monitoring Services

Openness Profile

Metadata Enrichment Services

News

News

Events

Newsletter

The project website is hosted by ATHENA RC, Greece and administered by CNR, Italy.

The website will be also linked to other relevant websites to help stakeholders navigate the constellation of initiatives related to Research Assessment (a map of the existing and previous projects will be built leveraging on the results of the landscaping exercise of WP2).

A social media strategy has been developed to complement the project web impact and is detailed in the section.

○ 3.3 Social media strategy

GraspOS social media accounts were set up to reach and address various groups of stakeholders with different needs and interests across the European research landscape. We expect social media to allow us to reach broader audiences than through traditional dissemination activities and to achieve the objectives listed below. All social media channels are administered and maintained by CNR, Italy.

- **Raise awareness about the project's concept and main goals.** In the initial stages of the project, the objective is to inform about the project and to increase and broaden the project's audience.
- **Build a community.** GraspOS will maximise community outreach and engagement through its social media channels. Social media will also be used to promote collaborations through the exchange of information, ideas and opinions.
- **Increase visibility and generate traffic to the GraspOS website.**
- **Promote and inform about GraspOS activities and events.** The project's social media channels are used to share project surveys, workshops and events.
- **Analyse the effectiveness and impact of our social media communication activities.** GraspOS will verify the impact of its social media presence by periodically

reporting on engagement metrics using the tools provided by each social media platform.

- **Promote the EC and the EOSC.**

To achieve the aforementioned objectives, a strategy was set up and implemented internally with the Content planning tool (specific sections of interest here are reported in Annexes 3, 4 and 5). The purpose of this tool is mainly to facilitate the organisation of Task 6.1 by planning and keeping record of the content published across the various GraspOS online channels (website, 3 social media channels).

In order to **maximise the outreach** of GraspOS communication activities, **reach broader audiences** and **strengthen synergies with key stakeholders**, we rely on the broad networks of the Consortium. The Consortium's online information and relevant, external stakeholders' social media information is gathered along with a list of frequently used hashtags and high-impact accounts that communicate on Open Science and RRA on Twitter. This ensures we effectively raise interest in the project by targeting the right stakeholder groups. For internal purposes, an internal calendar with relevant events in the world of Open Science and RRA was set up. It allows the task leaders to be up to date and aware of interesting initiatives and events and so as to promote them accordingly.

In the first months of the project 3 social media channels were set up: Twitter, Mastodon and a LinkedIn group. It was decided to make use of OpenAIRE's Youtube channel to make available and disseminate GraspOS training activities and video tutorials which will start at M12. Information on the GraspOS social media channels is reported below.

■ 3.3.1 Twitter

Creation: January 2023

URL: https://twitter.com/GraspOS_project

User name: @GraspOS_project

Display name: GraspOS

Number of followers: 247

Figure 8 GraspOS Twitter account

As of 28 June 2023, we have published or reposted 90 tweets on Twitter since the creation of the GraspOS project account. The main topics we communicate through Twitter focus on raising awareness on the project's objectives and activities, on events involving GraspOS partners or on relevant events and initiatives in the world of Open Science and RRA. In the perspective of building and strengthening connections with major actors in the field, GraspOS also reposts content from project partners and external, related research infrastructures, projects and initiatives.

The internal strategy to communicate efficiently on Twitter to reach our target stakeholders and build a community has been detailed in the previous section and is illustrated in Annex 4.

Twitter analytics for the GraspOS account are retrieved monthly. Figure 9 below reports the three top tweets which spurred the most interactions and the overall engagement rate in M5.

Figure 9 Twitter analytics in M5

■ 3.3.2 LinkedIn group

Creation: January 2023

URL: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/9303131/>

Name: GraspOS

Number of members: 37

Figure 10 GraspOS LinkedIn Group

As of 28 June 2023, we have published 8 posts on LinkedIn since the creation of the project group. The aim of the LinkedIn group is to have a space for the GraspOS community that enables mutual learning and sharing of experiences. The main activities we communicate on in the LinkedIn group focus on raising stakeholders' interest and boosting their engagement towards GraspOS project consultations (surveys, CoP, training).

It is worth mentioning that the purpose of the LinkedIn group differs from that of the other 3 social media accounts such as Twitter and Mastodon. The audience of the group is much smaller which could give way to interesting interactions within this space in the future. In the initial phase of the project, we concentrated on building visibility on Twitter given that users are generally directed to the LinkedIn group from the Twitter account. We expect the frequency of publications to increase in line with the advancement of the various project activities.

■ 3.3.3 Mastodon

Creation: May 2023

URL: <https://scicomm.xyz/@graspos>

User name: @GraspOS

Display name: GraspOS

Number of followers: 42

Figure 11 GraspOS Mastodon account

As of 28 June 2023, we have published and reposted 13 posts on Mastodon since the creation of the project account. The main objective of GraspOS is to stay in touch with the active community of former Twitter users who have moved towards Mastodon, a decentralised and open source network. Many researchers working or interested in Open Science are among them. We will make use of this account to inform interested stakeholders about the activities and developments of the project.

As with the Twitter account, the most significant hashtags that have the greatest impact in the world of Open Science and RRA are used within the posts. To facilitate the use of high impact hashtags and relevant handles to mention GraspOS partners and boost related projects and initiatives, we draw from our internal organisation explained in section 3.3. .

■ 3.3.4 Action plan overview

Table 5 below resumes the objectives and action plan for the 3 GraspOS social media channels.

Table 5 Action plan for GraspOS social media channels

Social Media channel	Objectives	Action Plan	Future actions
Twitter	Raise awareness of project, optimise visibility to reach a wide audience and maximise impact. Build a community.	Regular project updates on a weekly basis including relevant upcoming events to maintain interest especially during the first months of the project. Collaborate closely with OpenAIRE and relevant actors such as CoARA and DORA through reposts.	Publication of posts will increase in line with the achieved project results. Specific communication and dissemination plan will be set up and implemented for project results.
Linkedin	Promote the project within a circle of professionals i.e. a more targeted audience, informing about project activities and results. Foster engagement and participation for project consultations.	In the initial stages of the project follow key accounts, monthly posts about the projects' developments and activities. Engage with a small but focused group, prepare for the launch of future activities such as the CoP, training events.	Publication of posts will increase in line with achieved project results. Create a mutual-sharing of experiences environment on which other project consultations can rely on (CoP, training events).
Mastodon	Raise awareness about the project activities, keep in touch with relevant stakeholders.	Regular project updates consistent with the publication of Twitter posts. Engage with the community by inviting users to participate in project consultations.	Publication of posts will increase in line with project progress and achieved results.

○ 3.4 Newsletter

In order to inform GraspOS stakeholders on the advancements and results of the project, a monthly newsletter will be shared from M6 onwards. The newsletter will be hosted in the News section of the project website.

To engage subscribers and maximise the outreach of the newsletter, the GraspOS communications team (WP6) will systematically rely on the existing networks of partners of the consortium following the strategy presented at the beginning of Section 3.1.

In the initial stage of the project, the newsletter will focus on promoting GraspOS activities, progress and people and will also include a calendar of upcoming events in the Open Science and RRA ecosystem. Ideas of content to include in future newsletters also include a corner to

boost stakeholder engagement (in relation to the CoP, project surveys and workshops) and a corner to promote external initiatives relevant to GraspOS activities.

A specific communication campaign has been created to give visibility to GraspOS team members and to promote the project pilots, it will be implemented in M6. The campaign will take the form of informal interviews with the double aim to provide stakeholders with an insight on GraspOS activities in a narrative manner and to populate the newsletter with original content.

○ 3.5 Events

Two GraspOS webinars will be organised in the second half of the year with the aim to establish a dialogue with the broader community. They will be in an online format to save costs and allow for a wider participation. Renowned experts from the field will be invited to give presentations. The plan is to organise two webinars each year. A final face to face event (expected number of participants at least 100) will be organised towards the end of the project targeting RPOs and RFOs.

The project partners will be attending **external events**, including conferences and workshops addressing topics related to research careers and incentives, research assessment of Open Science and EOSC related events to present the results of the project and to understand how the landscape is developing.

In the first months of the project, GraspOS was presented in 5 events:

- On 15 March 2023 Janne Pölönen from TSV participated in the UKRN online workshop “Indicators for Open Research” and presented the Open Science Assessment Framework (OSAF) which will be developed in GraspOS as a toolkit to assist Open Science-aware RRA approaches. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7752573>
- On 28 May - 1 June 2023 Thanasis Vergoulis and Serafeim Chatzopoulos from Athena Research Center held a presentation on Piloting topic-aware research impact assessment features in BIP! Services at the Extended Semantic Web Conference 2023 and participated in the posters and demos sessions. <https://zenodo.org/record/7984968#.ZHdarexBzPY>. The presentation gave way to a publication available here: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2305.06047>.
- On 31 May - 1 June 2023 Laura Himanen from CSC attended the Spring 2023 EuroCRIS Membership meeting in Brussels and presented the activities planned in Pilot A of GraspOS project. <https://meeting.eurocris.org/CSC2.pdf>
- On 5 June 2023 at the Italian Tripartite Assembly for the EOSC, Francesca Di Donato from CNR represented GraspOS with a poster focusing on two pilot studies.
- On 19 - 23 June 2023 at the EGI Conference 2023 Chiara Di Giambattista from UNIBO presented a poster.

4 submissions were made to international events, all of which have already been accepted:

- On 2 July 2023 Thanasis Vergoulis and Andrea Mannocci will attend the ISSI conference (https://cns-iu.github.io/workshops/2023-07-02_issii/) and present a tutorial "Transitioning towards Open Scientometrics with Open Science Graphs".
- On 23-25 October 2023 Laurent Romary will participate in the session in Evaluation in Informatics of the 19th European Computer Science Summit "Informatics: Shaping the Future", presenting Pilot G of the project.
- 25-27 September 2023, Open Science FAIR Conference 2023 "CHARTING THE COURSE: REIMAGINING OPEN SCIENCE FOR NEXT GENERATIONS", organised by OpenAIRE and the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology.
- 27-29 September 2023, 27th International Conference on Science, Technology and Innovation Indicators organised by CWTS in collaboration with the European Network of Indicator Developers, Leiden. The GraspOS session will focus on "Research(er) evaluation at the interface of open science and responsible research assessment".

An internal calendar of relevant events that GraspOS partners can attend has been set up internally and is regularly kept up to date. It is copied in Annex 5.

In addition, GraspOS partners participate or plan to contribute to the following WGs:

- UNESCO Open Science WG, (<https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science>)
- G7 OSWG, (https://www8.cao.go.jp/cstp/kokusaiteki/g7_2023/annex1_os.pdf)
- OPERAS SIGs (<https://operas-eu.org/special-interest-groups/>)
- EOSC Task Forces (<https://eosc.eu/eosc-task-forces>)
- future CoARA WG
- future CoP of GraspOS

○ 3.6 Publications

The project aims to publish at least four research outputs (e.g., scientific articles, conference proceedings). They will be published in OA journals and platforms and/or stored in OA repositories with the aim to ensure wide dissemination, long-term availability and preservation of GraspOS outputs.

In the first phase of the project, one peer-reviewed publication has been published: Chatzopoulos, S., Vichos, K., Kanellos, I., and Vergoulis, T., "Piloting topic-aware research impact assessment features in BIP! Services", arXiv e-prints, 2023. doi:10.48550/arXiv.2305.06047.

The following publication venues are envisaged by GraspOS:

- OA journals
- OA platforms with or without peer review
- OA repositories like Zenodo
- Open Research Europe platform

- Horizon Results platform

As of now, the main dissemination and exploitation channels envisioned for GraspOS outputs are Zenodo and Open Research Europe.

Zenodo

Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) is “an open, dependable repository for all scholarship, enabling researchers from all disciplines to share and preserve their research outputs, regardless of size or format. Free to upload and free to access, Zenodo makes scientific outputs of all kinds citable, shareable and discoverable for the long term.”⁷

Zenodo will be used to disseminate project outputs such as deliverables, conference and research papers, and posters to make them publicly available. The repository attributes a DOI to each output deposited which ensures long term accessibility. When available, the authors' ORCID (<https://orcid.org/>) ID will be added. All project outputs will be indexed in the two communities curated by GraspOS.

- The GraspOS community (https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos_project/) collects all project outputs including deliverables.
- The Open Science and Responsible Research Assessment community (https://zenodo.org/communities/open_science_rra/) collect research outputs on the topic, including research which is not produced within GraspOS but is of interest for the community.

Open Research Europe

Open Research Europe is “an open access publishing platform for the publication of research stemming from Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe and/or Euratom funding across all subject areas.”⁸

GraspOS will favour the use of the Open Research Europe publishing platform as it provides a space for Horizon Europe projects to share their results rapidly and ensures compliance with the OA requirements in the Grant Agreement .

○ 3.7 Stakeholder consultation

A GraspOS Community of practice (CoP) will be set up in M6 and will officially kick off in M9. The CoP will consist of actors involved in Open Science practices and in developing new

⁷ <https://www.openaire.eu/zenodo/>

⁸ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/about/>

recognition and reward systems. It will bring together diverse groups of actors involved in the design, development, testing and validation of the infrastructure.

9 pilot studies will be carried out to co-design, showcase, validate and evaluate Open Science-aware RRA indicators, tools and services, representing three levels of Open Science-aware research assessment. The 9 pilots will organise targeted workshops with national and institutional stakeholders also including individuals. Each pilot also aims at organising interviews, surveys and focus groups with relevant stakeholders. A promotion campaign presenting the pilot activities in the form of interviews has been set up with the aim to start raising interest in their developments. The campaign is expected to be shared across project partners' online channels and will start at M6.

○ 3.8 Training

Seven training tutorials will be developed to educate the pilot participants and the external stakeholders on the benefits of adopting the new OSAF and on how to use the services and the infrastructure developed by WP3 and WP4. The activity will start at M12, the training tutorials will be accessible on Youtube and will be disseminated across all GraspOS online channels. In addition, a separate course on the OSAF will also be devised which will be hosted on the OpenPlato platform as a self-paced learning resource. More detail on these activities can be found in Deliverable 6.3 Community engagement and training activities plan (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8096385).

○ 3.9 Success stories

Each pilot will produce success stories to promote the results of the pilot. Success stories will be used to encourage new stakeholders with similar needs to reform their research assessment practices. The success stories will be published on the GraspOS website and disseminated through the GraspOS online channels.

○ 3.10 Final Brief

A final report will be produced by the project at M34 with guidelines and lessons learnt to be left as legacy to future initiatives and also to relevant stakeholders. It will be disseminated through all of GraspOS channels to maximise exploitation.

• 4. Alignment with the communication of GraspOS partners and related infrastructures and projects

We aim to **align the GraspOS communication strategy with the communication of GraspOS consortium partners**. This helps give more voice to the individual partners and allows us to keep partners actively involved in communication and dissemination activities. We encourage partners to spread the news published on the GraspOS communication channels through their own institutional channels, in their own languages.

In order to facilitate the sharing of GraspOS information from WP6 towards external stakeholders, their online information is collected in a shared file (Annex 4). The purpose of this file is mainly to make it easier for T6.1 leader to tag and link to relevant institutional accounts in the project's online and social media communication so as to maximise our outreach. In addition, a smaller group of project partners are used as more frequent relays, especially OpenAIRE and OPERAS with whom specific activities are coordinated on a monthly basis in order to align communication on topics of interest and to broaden the communication networks of GraspOS.

Alignment with external actors is carried out through the online and social media strategy through mutual collaboration in sharing relevant information. The key stakeholders GraspOS aims to connect and interact with are detailed in section 2.

Since January 2023, WP6 members have been taking part in the EOSC-A WG on Communication and Engagement for Horizon Europe INFRAEOSC projects with the aim to align communication strategies, build on each others' experience and enable collaborations between projects. The WG includes 18 projects who meet monthly and share planning and communication tools such as the EOSC Forum (<https://forum.eosc.eu/>) to join forces.

At the project level, a list of dissemination channels has been set up and will continue to be updated in the next phase of the project. The purpose of this file is to collect the mailing lists and dissemination channels to which project partners can share relevant results and boost participation in the case of project consultations. We expect this file to reflect the wide networks of stakeholders GraspOS Consortium is in contact with and the outreach of the dissemination activities.

• 5. Challenges

The potential challenges related to communication and how they can be addressed are identified below.

Alignment with existing initiatives. A variety of initiatives are currently working towards reforming research assessment. To achieve the project objectives, GraspOS will align with ongoing initiatives and learn from and reuse the achievements of past projects.

Large project with a large consortium. The GraspOS consortium includes 18 partners. To ensure a positive impact on the implementation of the project and a correct flow of information between the wide range of partners and stakeholders, regular internal meetings and communications within the GraspOS team have been set up .

Multi-Stakeholder environment. The project involves many countries and relative perspectives and workflows. To ensure an equal participation and engagement of societal actors in the GraspOS ecosystem and to overcome any potential management issues, needs and opinions of all stakeholders have been considered with regular and continuous circulation of pieces of information.

Collection and storage of personal data and contact details is essential to widen GraspOS network and potential users. This includes, but isn't limited to, the following cases:

- Visits to GraspOS website
- Visits to GraspOS Social Media channels
- Online surveys
- Newsletter subscription
- Participation in the GraspOS Community of Practice
- Registration for GraspOS events and initiatives

Collection and storage of personal data should be handled with care. In order to ensure compliance with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), we have started to identify the following parameters, which will be considered in each occasion personal data will be collected.

- Purpose of collecting the data
- Tools used to collect the data
- Who collects the data and how
- Who stores the data, where, and for how long

We are currently setting up GDPR-compliant data collection and storage procedures for the next phases of the project, in particular in view of the launch of the GraspOS newsletter and Community of Practice in M6.

• 6. Exploitation Plan

GraspOS has developed an exploitation plan to leverage the project's outcomes and propel its objectives forward. The primary aim of GraspOS is to establish a tailored federated infrastructure, serving as a dataspace specifically designed for measuring Open Science

indicators within the realm of RRA. The exploitation plan is strategically structured into two distinct but complementary strands, ensuring the successful utilisation of the project's results.

The first strand focuses on the technical exploitation of tools and services, supporting the efficient functioning of the dataspace within the federated infrastructure. This includes the seamless integration and interoperability of these tools and services, allowing for seamless data exchange and analysis. Concurrently, the second strand concentrates on the adoption and implementation of indicators for RRA, which are collaboratively designed throughout the project's duration. This collaborative approach ensures that the indicators accurately reflect the needs and priorities of the research community, enhancing stakeholder participation and ownership in the evaluation process.

By strategically emphasising these aspects, GraspOS aims to maximise the impact and value derived from its outcomes. The project is committed to actively engaging stakeholders, promoting openness, and facilitating the integration of its tools and services into the EOSC ecosystem. GraspOS will actively pursue collaborations with international partners and organisations to foster knowledge exchange, ensuring global applicability and reach of its results. Through these collaborations, the project seeks to contribute to the harmonisation of research evaluation practices and drive the adoption of open science principles on a global scale.

○ 6.1 Technical exploitation Plan: Interoperability and Integration in EOSC

The technical exploitation plan of GraspOS focuses on ensuring the interoperability of its tools and services for RRA while aiming for seamless integration within the EOSC.

GraspOS recognises the importance of collaboration with infrastructure and service providers, including OpenAIRE, OPERAS, and EGI, who share a vested interest in exploiting the services and tools developed throughout the project. To maximise the uptake and impact of the project's outcomes, these partners, along with their extensive networks of over 100 organisations, will play a central role in the operational infrastructure, facilitating broad impact and exploitation.

A key objective of GraspOS is the full integration of its infrastructure into the EOSC through the establishment of an open research assessment dataspace. This integration will ensure the interoperability of GraspOS with diverse CRIS and national providers, enabling seamless data exchange and analysis. By embracing interoperability, GraspOS aims to eliminate silos and promote the harmonisation of research assessment practices across different systems and stakeholders.

In addition, the project will actively collaborate with relevant standardisation bodies and research infrastructures to establish and promote the adoption of open metrics and evaluation practices. By aligning with existing standards and frameworks, GraspOS seeks to

facilitate the integration and interoperability of its tools and metrics with other research evaluation systems. This collaborative approach ensures that GraspOS can effectively contribute to the broader research ecosystem and promote consistent and transparent evaluation practices.

By prioritising interoperability and integration within the EOSC, GraspOS not only enhances the value and usability of its tools and services but also fosters a more sustainable e-infrastructure for Responsible Research Assessment. Through seamless data exchange, alignment with existing standards, and collaboration with key stakeholders (e.g the internal Pilots, the CoP, other relevant EU-funded projects, and CoARA), GraspOS aims to make a significant contribution to the advancement of Open Science and the responsible evaluation of research within the European research landscape.

○ 6.2 Tailoring Adoption and Implementation of Open Science indicators

As part of the exploitation plan, GraspOS recognises the importance of tailoring the adoption and implementation of the Open Science indicators to ensure their effective use. This involves active engagement with various stakeholders and community-driven initiatives to foster ownership and participation in the evaluation process.

To achieve this, GraspOS will collaborate closely with relevant initiatives for RRA such as CoARA and projects such as OPUS. By leveraging the expertise and resources from them, GraspOS will facilitate the dissemination and adoption of the services and tools developed for RRA. This collaboration will be instrumental in driving the uptake of assessment protocols and metrics within RPOs and RFOs. Moreover, the GraspOS pilot owners will exploit these protocols and metrics within their own organisations, and their positions within national Open Science bodies will enable them to advocate for and promote the results more effectively.

GraspOS places a strong emphasis on community engagement and co-design. The project aims to actively involve communities in the co-creation of a dataspace that supports evaluation for individual researchers, research groups, institutions, and systemic stakeholders such as RFOs and policymakers. This participatory approach ensures that stakeholders have a sense of ownership in the evaluation process and that the developed tools align with their specific needs and priorities.

Furthermore, GraspOS prioritises the enhanced participation of relevant stakeholders in the development of indicators for openness profiles within the OSAF. By collaborating with these stakeholders, GraspOS ensures that the indicators accurately reflect the diverse requirements and priorities of the research community. Additionally, the project will exploit the OSAF in pilot activities, evaluating various parameters across research disciplines, career stages, institutions, and systemic levels. This exploitation of the OSAF as well as the landscape

analysis from WP5 and WP2 will generate valuable insights into the framework's effectiveness and contribute to its continuous improvement.

To foster community-based validation, GraspOS will organise events where policy reports, key initiatives in RRA, pilot activities, best practices, lessons learned, training sessions, and the final report of GraspOS will be shared and discussed. These events will serve as platforms for active participation and feedback from the research community, enhancing the project's impact and relevance.

Through tailoring the adoption and implementation of Open Science indicators, active community engagement, and validation processes, GraspOS ensures that its services and tools effectively meet the needs of stakeholders, promote open research practices, and contribute to the advancement of Responsible Research Assessment within the research community.

● Conclusions

The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan outlines the strategy for the implementation of all the communication activities and the dissemination and exploitation measures of the GraspOS project. The communication and dissemination plan represents an effective implementation tool to achieve the aims of promoting the project and maximising the impact of its key results. The exploitation plan will both ensure the technical operation of the tools and services and the adoption and implementation of RRA indicators developed within GraspOS.

● References

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4. Corporate Design Manual of the EOSC Association, September 2022. https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/2022-09/EOSC%20Corporate%20Design%20Manual_HR.pdf
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6. United Nations, Guidelines for gender-inclusive language in English.
<https://www.un.org/en/gender-inclusive-language/guidelines.shtml>
7. Zenodo community for GraspOS outputs and deliverables.
https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos_project/
8. Zenodo community on Open Science and Responsible Research Assessment.
https://zenodo.org/communities/open_science_rra/

- **Annexes**

- Annex 1 GraspOS Brand guidelines

BASE LOGO

Celestial Blue

HEX	3192d0
RGB	49,146,208
HSB	203,76,81
CMYK	74,31,0,0

Mulberry

HEX	ae538e
RGB	174,83,142
HSB	320,52,68
CMYK	34,81,15,0

BLACK AND WHITE

graspōs
open research assessment dataspacē

graspōs
open research assessment dataspacē

LOGO DO

graspōs
open research assessment dataspacē

graspōs
open research assessment dataspacē

LOGO DONT

Don't stretch or condense

Don't recolor the logo

Don't add any effects

Don't change the placemnt of any elements

Don't alter the typeface

Don't use outline or stroke

Don't use a busy background

Don't rote

Don't use elements alone

LAYOUT

EXCLUSION ZONE

MINIMUM LOGO SIZE

300 PIXELS

COLORS

PRIMARY

SECONDARY

- Annex 2 Planning and reporting tool for communication and dissemination activities
-

Status	Date	Events	Name of the event	Language	Main target	Engage additional info	Venue (if applicable)	Main organizer	Website	Type of participation/contribution	Day and time of event/GraspOS contribution	GraspOS number and contact	Added value for GraspOS	Estimated outreach	Link to the presentation slides	Materials deposited on GraspOS (year/week)
in progress	10 October 2023	Virtual event (external)	FAIR-IMPACT Roadshow in Bethesda	English	Researchers (individuals/groups)	Researchers will facilitate, but it is a virtual event	Serbian institution	University of Belgrade		Assess the status of OS practices and regulations in Serbia. examine on some	October 10th, 11am CEST	Pagan Ivanovic	Presentation of the WP2 landscape analysis	50		
in progress	26-27 October 2023	Workshop (external)	Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata 2023	English	Researchers (individuals/groups)		Bologna, Italy	University of Bologna	https://www.informatica.unibo.it/it/2023/10/26-27-ottobre-2023-workshop-on-open-citations-and-open-scholarly-metadata-2023/				100			
in progress	27-29 September 2023	International event (external)	19th European Computer Science Summit	English			Edinburgh, Scotland	Informatics Europe	https://www.infomatics-europe.org/2023/	1h30 session on evaluation in informatics		Laurent Romary	presentation of Pilot G	Number of participants		
in progress	25-27 September 2021	International event (external)	31st 2023 27th International Conference on Science, Technology and Innovation	English			Netherlands	CWTS						Number of participants		
in progress	25-27 September 2021	International event (external)	Open Science FAIR "CHARTING THE COURSE" (OPEN SCIENCE FOR INNOVATION)	English			Madrid, Spain	OpenDRIE	https://www.openendrieproject.eu/	Internal scientific knowledge presentation with assessment workshops		Thanasia Vergoulis, Andrea Mannocci		Number of participants		
in progress	2 July 2023	International event (external)	United Transposing towards Open Science at OS conference 2023	English			Bloomington, Indiana, USA	Indiana University	https://osconf2023.indiana.edu/	Poster presentation (mentioning GraspOS)		Chiara Di Lorenzo (OpenCitations)				
in progress	19-23 June 2023	International event (external)	EGG Conference	English			Poznan, Poland	EGG	https://www.egg-conference.eu/	presentation GraspOS (10 min)		Thanasia Vergoulis, Clifford Tatum	Presentation of CS Open Science profile	15 high level participants		
in progress	15-16 June 2023	Coordination meeting	Coordination meeting EDC-related projects	English			Brussels, Belgium	EDSC Association								
in progress	7 June 2023	Organisation meeting	ACM Publication Board Meeting	English	Other	Publishers	San Francisco, US	ACM								
completed	5 June 2023	International event (external)	ITAEOS-2023 Italian Tripartite Assembly for the EDC National event	English	EDSC ecosystem		Rome, Italy	EDSC Association	https://www.edsc-association.eu/	Poster to present GraspOS pilot D and G		Natalia Marola			Yes	
completed	28 May - 1 June 2023	International event (external)	Extended Semantic Web Conference 2023	English			Herzlisson, Greece	EDSC Association	https://www.semanticweb.org/track/2023/	Poster presentation and participation to the interactivities		Thanasia Vergoulis, Charitopolis	Researchable research assessment principles for present (researcher) and the activities	Number of participants	https://www.semanticweb.org/track/2023/	Yes
completed	31 May - 1 June	Spring 2023 eunCIS Membership meeting	Spring 2023 eunCIS Membership meeting	English			Brussels, Belgium	EDSC Association	https://www.eun-cis.eu/	Possible sessions on GraspOS projects (linked to the EDC-SA WG on Community and						
proposed	22-23 May 2023	International event (external)	EDSC Association 6th General Assembly	English			Brussels, Belgium	EDSC Association	https://www.edsc-association.eu/							
aborted	16 May 2023	Virtual event (external)	DOBA at 10: Looking back at the history and forward to the future of research assessment (plenary session)	English			online	DOBA	https://www.doba-eu.org/2023/05/16-doba-at-10-looking-back-at-the-history-and-forward-to-the-future-of-research-assessment/				30 participants	https://www.doba-eu.org/2023/05/16-doba-at-10-looking-back-at-the-history-and-forward-to-the-future-of-research-assessment/	no presentations with slides from partners	
completed	21-22 March 2023	Virtual event (external)	Indicators for Open Research	English			online	The RWI - Leibniz Information Centre for Economics	https://www.rwi-leibniz.de/en/indicators-for-open-research/		31 March 2023 13:15 PM and 22 March 2023 13:15 PM	Enrico Ana Boriovec	presentation of GraspOS		https://www.rwi-leibniz.de/en/indicators-for-open-research/	Yes
completed	15 March 2023	Virtual event (external)	Indicators for Open Research	English			online	UK Reproducibility Network	https://www.ukrn.ac.uk/indicators-for-open-research/			Janne Palonen	presentation of GraspOS		https://www.ukrn.ac.uk/indicators-for-open-research/	Yes
completed	24-25 February 2023	International event (external)	MCAA annual conference 2023 - Parallel session: "Translating research assessment into practice"	English	Researchers (individuals/groups)	Researchers	Cordoba, Spain (physical)	Marie Curie Alumni Association	https://www.mcaa.eu/en/2023/02/24-25-february-2023-mcaa-annual-conference-2023-parallel-session-translating-research-assessment-into-practice/	Discussion on Research Assessment	15 February 2023 11:12 AM	Guilia Malaguarra	dissemination and awareness about the goal of the project	80+ online participants and recording	https://www.mcaa.eu/en/2023/02/24-25-february-2023-mcaa-annual-conference-2023-parallel-session-translating-research-assessment-into-practice/	no slides

- Annex 3 Content planning tool: WP6 channels for communication and dissemination

WP6 communication dissemination channels

Name	Website	Twitter account	LinkedIn account	Mastodon
PARTNERS' ONLINE CHANNELS				
GrasPOS	https://graspos.eu/	@GrasPOS_project	https://www.linkedin.com/gi	@graspos@scicomm.xyz
CNR-ILC Website	http://www.ilc.cnr.it/en	@CNRsocial_	https://www.linkedin.com/cc	
CNR-ISTI Website	https://www.isti.cnr.it/en/	@IstiCnr		
CNR-IRPPS Website	https://www.irpps.cnr.it/	@CNRirpps		
OpenAIRE Website	https://www.openaire.eu/	@OpenAIRE_eu	https://www.linkedin.com/cc	@openaire_eu@bird.makeup
OPERAS	https://operas-eu.org/	@OPERASEU	https://www.linkedin.com/cc	@operaseu@bird.makeup
Athena Research Center Website	https://www.athenarc.gr/en/home	@athenaRICinfo	https://www.linkedin.com/cc	@athenaricinfo@bird.makeup
UEFISCDI Website	https://uefiscdi.gov.ro/	@uefiscdi	https://www.linkedin.com/cc	@uefiscdi@bird.makeup
CSC - IT Center for Science We	https://www.csc.fi/	@CSCfi	https://www.linkedin.com/cc	
University of Eastern Finland \	https://www.uef.fi/fi	@UniEastFinland	https://www.linkedin.com/sc	
INRAE, Institut national de rec	https://www.inrae.fr/en	@INRAE_France	https://www.linkedin.com/cc	
INRIA, Institut national de rech	https://www.inria.fr/fr	@Inria	https://www.linkedin.com/cc	
Centre for Science and Technol	https://www.cwts.nl/	@cwtsleiden	https://www.linkedin.com/cc	@cwts@social.cwts.nl
Alma Mater Studiorum - Univé	https://www.unibo.it/it	@Unibo	https://www.linkedin.com/sc	@CscC@sciences.social
University of Utrecht Website	https://www.uu.nl/en	@UniUtrecht	https://www.linkedin.com/gi	@utrechtuniversity@akad
CESNET Website	https://www.cesnet.cz/	@CESNET_cz	https://www.linkedin.com/cc	
EGI Foundation Website	https://www.egi.eu/egi-foundation/	@EGI_einfra	https://www.linkedin.com/cc	
Greek Research & Technology	https://grnet.gr/en/	@grnet_gr	https://www.linkedin.com/cc	
The Scientific and Technologic	https://www.tubitak.gov.tr/en	@Tubitak	https://www.linkedin.com/cc	
Tieteellisten seurain valtuusku	https://www.tsv.fi/	@tsv_media		
Faculty of Chemistry Universit	https://www.chem.bg.ac.rs/	@HemjiskFak_UB	https://www.linkedin.com/c	
EXTERNAL CHANNELS				
EOSC Association Forum, Horizon Europe projects group	https://forum.eosc.eu/		https://www.linkedin.com/c	
Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment	https://coara.eu/	@CoARAssessment	https://www.linkedin.com/c	
OPUS Project	https://opusproject.eu/	@OpusEu	https://www.linkedin.com/c	

- Annex 4 Content planning tool: GraspOS social media networks

Name	Handle	number of followers	main topics	Mastodon (y/n)	If yes, link
Open and Universal Science Project	@OpusEu	502	Reform the assessment of research at Research Performing Organisations and Research Funding Organisations	no	
CoAllition for Advancing Research Assessment	@CoARAssessment	919	Research assessment practices	no	
OpenAIRE	@OpenAIRE_eu	16,9 K	Open scholarship, discoverability, accessibility, shareability, reusability, reproducibility and monitoring of data-driven research results	no	
Declaration on Research Assessment	@DORAssessment	14,9 K	Research Assessment	no	
EOSC Association	@eoscassociation	1,831	Open science, government of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)	no	
European University Association	@EUA	20 K	Individual institutions and the higher education sector	yes	
FORCE11 - Future of Research Communication and e-Scholarship	@FORCE11rescomm	5,131	Research communication, e-scholarship	no	
Center for Open Science	@OSFramework	36.6 K	Openness, integrity and reproducibility in science	no	
ROpenSci	@rOpenSci	35.8 K	Open and reproducible research using shared data and reusable software	yes	@OpenSci@hachyderm.io
Research on Research Institute	@RoRIInstitute	5,283	Transformational research on research systems, cultures and decision-making	no	
SPARC	@SPARC_NA	17.8 K	Open Research, Education	yes	@sparc@mastodon.social
Open Science MOOC	@OpenScienceMOOC	9,031	Open Research	no	
Open Access 2020	@oa2020ini	2,768	Open Access	no	
Open Science ASAP	@openscienceASAP	547	Open Science	no	
Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative	@COKIproject	591	Analysis and Evaluation of Open Knowledge in higher education	no	
COAllitionS	@cOAllitionS_OA	5,543	Open Access	no	
OntoCommons	@ontocommons	675	FAIR interoperable standardised ontology data-documentation for datasharing	no	
Leiden Madtrics	@LeidenMadtrics	1,577	Metrics and matter that matters in the science blog by @CWTSLeiden	yes	@leidenmadtrics@social.cwts.nl
UAS4EUROPE	@UAS4EUROPE	522	Applied research	no	
CESAER	@CESAER_SnT	1391	Universities of Science and Technology in Europe	yes	@CESAER@eupolicy.social
Coimbra Group	@CoimbraGroup	3735	Learning and Research	no	
OSEC 2022 - Paris Open Science European Conference	@Osec2022	1254	Open Science, transformation of the research and innovation ecosystem in Europe	no	
International Consortium of Research Staff Associations	@ICoRSA_News	930	Global research	no	
RRING Project	@RRING_PROJECT	1341	Responsible Research and Innovation	no	
International Conference on ICT	@ICTeSSH	327	Information-communication technologies enhanced Social Sciences and Humanities	no	
Science Europe	@ScienceEurope	13,7 K	Scientific Research	no	

Twitter high impact accounts on Open Science and RRA: People			For all WPE and partners' communication channels go to: GraspOS Channels for dissemination_WP6 tab.		Mastodon		If yes, link	
Name	handle	number of followers	Main topics		Mastodon	If yes, link		
Richard Poynder	@RickyPo	8,488	Open Science, Scholarly Communication		yes	@rickypo@activism.openworlds.info		
Elli Papadopoulou	@elli_lib	803	Open Science		no			
Thomas Neidenmark	@thomasneiden	750	Scholarly Communication		no			
Tony Ross-Heilauer	@tonyR_H	2,355	Open and reproducible research		yes	@tonyRH@mstdn.social		
Hans de Jonge	@HJdeJonge	1,699	Open Science		yes	@HJdeJonge@akademienl.social		
Maria J. Cruz	@gravana	1,839	Open Science policies, astrophysics		yes	@mariacruz@akademienl.social		
Niels Stern	@nielstern	977	Open Access, Open Science, Scholarly Communication		yes	@nielstern@mastodon.social		
Gareth O'Neill	@gtonell	1,720	Open Science		no			
Ross Mounce	@rmounce	7,002	Open Access Programmes		yes	@rmounce@mastodon.social		
Björn Brems	@brems	10,6 K	Open Science, neurogenetics		yes	@brems@mastodon.social		
Erin McKiernan	@emckiernan13	5,187	Open research		no			
James Morris	@PMorris88	542	Research Assessment, culture and infrastructure		no			
Jeroen Bosman	@jeroenbosman	6,293	Open Science, Open Access		yes	@jeroenbosman@akademienl.social		
Alexander Grossmann	@SciPubLab	4,015	Open Science, transparency, physics		no			
James Hardcastle	@JwHardcastle	841	Research metrics, assessment and Open Science		yes	@JamesHardcastle@mastodonapp.uk		
Sophie Gultton	@AltheaDelalune	227	Open Science		no			
Kwesi Sewe	@kwesibs	198	Open Science, Research Assessment		no			
Hanne Vanhaverbeke	@HanneloreVh	256	Open Science, Scholarly Communication, Research Assessment, Archaeology		no			
Beate Eillend	@BeateEillend	1,155	Open Access, Open Science, Research Assessment		no			
Julia Stern	@_julia_stern	779	Open Science		no			
Jess Butler	@jessButler284	1,389	Open Science		yes	@jessButler@mastodon.social		

Twitter INFRA EOSC Projects These are the projects with whom GraspOS collaborates through the HE C&E WG				Mastodon	If yes, link
Name of Project	handle	number of followers	Main topics		
AI4EOSC Artificial Intelligence for the European Open Science Cloud	@AI4EOSC	120	Services for the development of AI, ML and DL models and applications for the EOSC	yes	@ai4eosc@mastodon.social
AquaINFRA Infrastructure for Marine and Inland Water Research	@AquaInfraEU	106	Data and services to support marine and freshwater scientists and stakeholders	no	
Blue-Cloud2026 A Federated European FAIR and open Research Ecosystem for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters	@BlueCloudEU	1,520	FAIR and open Research Ecosystem for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters	no	
BeYond-COVID -- making infectious disease digital objects open and FAIR	@BYCOVID_eu	339	Open data on SARS-Cov-2 and other infectious diseases across scientific, medical, public health and policy domains	no	
CRAFT-OA Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access	@craftoa_project	70	OA Publishing, Open Science	yes	@craftoa@mastodon.online
e-IRGSP7 e-Infrastructure Reflection Group Support Programme 7	@eirgeu	724	European e-Infrastructure policymaking and the development of convergent and sustainable e-Infrastructure services	no	
EOSC4Cancer A European-wide foundation to accelerate data-driven cancer research	@EOSC4Cancer	238	Data-driven Cancer Research	yes	@eosc4cancer@europolicy.social
EOSC Future	@EOSCFuture	1,397	Extension of EOSC EIF, use of AAI, Accounting for services, usage from EOSC portal	no	
EuroScienceGateway			Federated open access computational infrastructure through Galaxy as a gateway for data resources , tools and applications by the FAIR principles	no	
FAIRCORE4EOSC Core Components Supporting a FAIR EOSC	@FAIRCORE4EOSC	413	Use of PID and OpenAIRE Graphs, RAID Infrastructure, PID and AAI infrastructures	no	
FAIR-EASE FAIR Earth Sciences & Environment services	@FAIR_EASE	165	Distributed and integrated services for observation and modelling of the earth system, environment and biodiversity	no	
FAIR IMPACT Expanding FAIR Solutions across EOSC	@fairimpact_eu	805	FAIR assessors	no	
RAISE Research Analysis Identifier System	@RaiseScience	75	Infrastructure for a distributed crowdsourced data processing system, moving from open data to open access data for processing	no	
SciLake	@SciLake_project	56	Data Lakes, Open Science, Research	no	
Skills4EOSC	@Skills4Eosc	441	Skills for researcher managers to use new generation metrics	no	

- Annex 5 Content planning tool: Shared calendar of events in the field of Open Science and RRA

Date	Title of the event	Type of event	Website	Target group	Where	Deadline for submission or registration	Organiser	Notes	added to website Events section	Link to published event on website
31 October - 03 November 2023	Scientometrics Using Open Data (course)	Training	https://www.cwts.nl/education/	Researchers	In-person		CWTS			https://graspos.eu/oras/events/conference/workshop-on-open-citations-open-scholarly-metadata-2023
26-27 October 2023	Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarship Metadata 2023	Workshop	https://workshop.oc.github.io/	Researchers	Hybrid		Open Citations		yes	
23-27 October 2023	Global Summit on Diamond Open Access	Conference/Workshop	https://globaldiamondoa.org/en/	RPOs/RFOs	In-person		Redalyc, Autonomous University of the State of Mexico, AMERICA, UNESCO, CLACSO, Action Plan for Diamond Open Access			
23-26 October 2023	SciDataCon 2023	Conference/Workshop	https://www.scidatacon.org/	All of them	Hybrid		International Science Council: CODATA (the ISC's Committee on Data) and the WDS (the ISC's World Data System International Programme Office).			
23-25 October 2023	19th European Computer Science Summit "Informatics: Shaping the Future"	Conference/Workshop	https://www.informatics-europe.eu/				Informatics Europe	11:30 session on evaluation in informatics as a preparation of the work in pilot on Laurent Rebry.	yes	https://graspos.eu/oras/events/conference/19th-european-computer-science-sum
23-24 October 2023	Second Annual Forum for Open Research in MENA	National event	https://forumforopenresearch.cc	RPOs/RFOs	Hybrid	Call for papers open until 31 June 2023	Knowledge E Foundation			
4-6 October 2023	5th International Open Search Symposium #osysym2023	Conference/Workshop	https://opensearchfoundation.org/	Researchers	In-person		Open Search Foundation	maybe hybrid		

Date	Title of the event	Type of event	Website	Target group	Where	Deadline for submission or registration	Organiser	Notes	added to website Events section	Link to published event on website
September										
27-29 September 2023	STI 2023	Conference/We binar	https://www.sti2023.org/	All of them					yes	https://graspos.eu/pr-ess/events/conferenc-ess/STI-2023
25-27 September 2023	OSFAIR 2023	Conference/We binar	https://www.opensciencefair.eu/	All of them					yes	
20-22 September 2023	EOSC Symposium	Conference/We binar	https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/	All of them	Hybrid					
19 September 2023	Spanish National Tripartite Event	National event	https://eosc.eu/events/nationalst	ESOC ecosystem						
13-15 September 2023	"PUBMET 2023 - The 10th Conference on Scholarly Communication in the Context of Open Science - Croatia"	Conference/We binar	https://pubmet2023.unid.hr/	Researchers						
August										
31 August 2023	Open Science Festival NL		https://opensciencefestival.nl/	Researchers	In-person					
July										
3 July 2023	Horizon Europe Open Science requirements in practice	Conference/We binar	https://www.openscience.eu/events	Researchers	Online		OpenAIRE			
2 July 2023	ISSI conference 2023. Tutorial "Transitioning towards Open Scientometrics with Open Science Graphs"	Conference/We binar	https://www.openscience.eu/events/webinar		Bloomington, Indiana, USA		Indiana University		yes	https://graspos.eu/pr-ess/events/conferenc-ess/ISSI-2023
June										
28 June 2023	UKRIO Webinar. Co-production: participant and stakeholder involvement in research.	Conference/We binar	https://ukrio.org/events/webinar	Researchers	Online		UK Research Integrity Office			
27-28 June 2023	Open Science Conference 2023	Conference/We binar	https://www.openscience-confer	All of them	Online		Leibniz Information Centre for Economics		yes	https://graspos.eu/pr-ess/events/conferenc-ess/open-science-conf-2023
19-20 June 2023	The Potential of Research Data	Conference/We binar	https://swedish-presidency.consil	Research infrastructure	In-person					
19-23 June 2023	EGI Conference 2023	International event (external)	https://www.egi.eu/events/egi2023/	All of them	Hybrid		EGI	Poster presentation (mentioning GrasPOS, Chiara Di Giambattista (OpenChallons))	yes	https://graspos.eu/pr-ess/events/conferenc-ess/egi-2023
13-14 June 2023	French National Tripartite Event	National event	https://eosc.eu/events/nationalst	ESOC ecosystem	Hybrid					

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Date	Title of the event	Type of event	Website	Target group	Where	Deadline for submission or registration	Organiser	Notes	added to website Events section	Link to published event on website
12 June 2023	We accelerate the transition to Open Science	Conference/webinar	https://eosc.eu/events/we-accelerate	ESOC ecosystem	In-person	Registration open until 7 June	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Swedish Research Council, EOOSC-Association		yes	https://graspos.eu/fair-events/conference-we-accelerate-the-transition-to-open-science
12-15 June 2023	Open Repositories 2023	Conference/webinar	https://or2023.openrepositories.org/	All of them	In-person		Stellenbosch University			
7 June 2023	Open Science – a general introduction	Workshop	https://www.uu.nl/en/events/wor	Researchers	In-person		Utrecht University Library			
5 June 2023	Italian Tripartite Assembly for the EOOSC	National event	https://eosc.eu/events/national-it	ESOC ecosystem	In-person					
31 May - 1 June	11th Annual Meeting of the Global Research Council	Conference/webinar	https://globalresearchcouncil.org					The meeting is addressing two topics: signing and promoting research, and climate change research		
31 May - 1 June	Spring 2023 euroCRIS Membership meeting	Conference/webinar	https://meeting.eurocris.org/		In-person			In person event in Brussels		
28 May - 1 June 2023	Extended Semantic Web Conference 2023	International event (external)	https://2023.eswc.conf.					GrasPOS/Lake contribution: 1 min presentation and participation to the interactive Posters and demos session: Thanasia Vergoulis, Serafeim Chatzopoulos		
31 May 2023	How to advocate for Open Education?	Conference/webinar	https://operas.eu.org/special-int	All of them	Online		https://2023.eswc-conferences.org/organising-a-committee/ OPERAS SIG "Advocacy"			
31 May 2023	Argos Community Call	Other	https://www.openaire.eu/events/	All of them	Online		OpenAIRE, Argos	Monthly calls on FAIR DMP requirements for Horizon Europe especially for researchers and RPOs.		
24 May 2023	UKRIO Annual Virtual Conference 2023: Research integrity, culture and confidence.	Conference/webinar	https://ukrio.org/events/annuals	RPOs/RFOs, researchers	Online		UK Research Integrity Office			
29 May 2023	Translating Open Science and FAIR policies into practice in Finland	Conference/webinar	https://ssi.eventilla.com/event/21	RPOs/RFOs	Online		Skills4EOOSC, EOOSC Finnish Forum			
22-23 May 2023	EOOSC Association General Assembly	Conference/webinar	https://eosc.eu/form/ga-fo-register	ESOC ecosystem	In-person		EOOSC Association			
18 May 2023	The future of peer review	Workshop	https://www.ukrn.org/event/ukrn	Researchers	Online		UKRN		yes	https://graspos.eu/fair-events/conference/future-of-peer-review
16 May 2023	EOOSC Future Use Case Event	Workshop	https://eosc.future.eu/events/fu	Researchers	Online		EOOSC Future			
16-17 May 2023	Open Science from Policy to Practice	Conference/webinar	https://openwetenskap.se/	Other	Hybrid		Swedish Research Council, National Library of Sweden, Swedish Museum of Natural History			

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16 May 2023	DORA at 10: Looking back at the history and forward to the future of research assessment (plenary session)	Conference/webinar	https://sfh.dora.org/2023/01/25/d6/	All of them	Online		DORA. Re ordering and materials available on their webpage .		yes	https://graspOS.eu/df-ast/events/conference-dora-at-10h-anniversary-10-2023
9-10 May 2023	Metascience Conference 2023	Conference/webinar	https://metascience.info/	All of them	Hybrid				yes	
17 April 2023	More Than our Rank Community calls	Conference/webinar	https://norms.net/more-than-our-rank/	RPOs/RFOs			organised by INORMS, recording available Siles L. Wältman on Zenodo.		no	
13 April 2023	Recognition and Rewards Festival	Workshop	https://recognitionrewards.nl/df-gamme-2023/	Researchers			recording available on the website with a report			
31 March 2023	The Rise of Responsible Metrics as a professional reform	Conference/webinar	https://www.cwts.nl/seminars/an	Researchers	MARCH		organised by CWTS, link to the paper discussed		no	